

INVESTIGATION OF THE EFFECT OF MULTI-WALLED CARBON NANOTUBES AND GRAPHENE NANO-PLATELETS ON INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF CFRP

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ABSTRACT

The present study attempts to investigate the influence of Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes (MWCNTs) and few layered Graphene Nano-Platelets (GNPs) on the interlaminar fracture properties of carbon fiber epoxy composites (CFRPs).

Towards this direction two amounts of each carbon nano-material were incorporated into the epoxy matrix by using the Dissolver Technique in order to succeed nanodoped matrices in contents of 0.5 and 1% wt. The prepared mixtures were used for the manual impregnation of unidirectional fabrics with a purpose of producing nano-modified prepregs. Neat epoxy was also used in order to obtain the reference material properties. For the production of composite panels a combination of compression molding and vacuum bagging was utilized.

The resistance to interlaminar crack propagation of the composites was defined by performing two types of fracture toughness experiments (Mode I/II tests). The Mode I fracture toughness, G_{IC} , was determined by using the double cantilever beam method, and was carried out in accordance with ASTM D5528. Mode II fracture toughness, G_{IIC} , was measured by using the three-point end-notched flexure (3ENF) method. Furthermore, Scanning Electron Microscopy was performed in order to examine the fracture surfaces of the failed specimens.

It was observed that both nano-fillers proved highly beneficial for the improvement of fracture properties of CFRPs. Also, the two nanoparticles have shown different behavior with their increasing content in the matrix. In particular, the increasing content of MWCNTs in the epoxy matrix caused further enhancement in fracture properties (G_{IC} and G_{IIC}) while the highest content of GNPs (1% wt.) showed decreased values in comparison with that of the 0.5% wt. GNP content.

Finally, in the case of Mode I tests the MWCNTs proved the most efficient fillers for the G_{IC} enhancement, achieving a 36% increase at 1% wt. In the case of Mode II tests the introduction of 0.5% wt. GNPs increased 50% the G_{IIC} of the final material. The positive contribution of nano-fillers in the fracture properties of CFRPs is due to the additional toughening mechanisms that are introduced during fracture, by the nano-phase of the multi-scale composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber-reinforced polymers (CFRP) have been widely used as structural components in many areas, including aerospace, automobile, sports and military industries due to their unique properties, such as high specific strength and stiffness. However, the out of plane properties is a limiting design factor in conventional composites because there are no fibers oriented in the thickness direction in order to sustain transverse loads. This poor out of plane performance of composites which is dominated by the low toughness of polymer matrix generally leads to interlaminar failures, such as delamination.

A considerable amount of research has been conducted regarding the improvement of interlaminar fracture toughness in order to avoid the aforementioned catastrophic type of failure. In the last decade,

the incorporation of nanoparticles into the epoxy matrices offers new possibilities toward this direction. The nano-phase controls the fracture behavior of the composites, by introducing additional energy dissipation mechanisms during fracture. Specifically, the addition of nano-inclusions contributes to the toughening of polymer matrix and to the improvement of fiber-matrix adhesion both of which lead to the enhancement of interlaminar fracture toughness. Thus multi-scale reinforced composites exhibit improved damage tolerance and fracture properties.

The most popular nanoparticles in this field are carbon nanotubes (CNTs) due to their outstanding mechanical, electrical and thermal properties. Also, their high aspect ratio and surface area make them unique. It has been widely reported in literature that the incorporation of CNTs into the matrix of FRPs strengthens the energy absorption abilities of the brittle polymer and the adhesion between fiber and matrix. Accordingly, interlaminar fracture of FRPs considerably enhanced with the inclusion of CNTs into the polymer resulting in an improvement of damage tolerance of composites. [1-5]

In recent years, there have been great interests in the application of graphite derivatives in composites [6-8] since they combine the the 2D layered structure of nanoclays with the superior mechanical, thermal and electrical properties of carbon nanotubes. The most widely used graphene nano-species (GNSs) are graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs). Specifically, GNPs are disk-shaped graphite particles which are usually obtained by rapid heating of a graphite intercalation compounds (GICs). The resulting material is composed of two or more layers of graphene planes; with a platelet thickness ranges from 0.34 to 100nm.

According to literature [9-16], GNSs seems to be very promising fillers for the production of nano-reinforced polymers and laminates with enhanced mechanical and fracture properties. Specifically, Jun Ma et al. referred that K_{IC} and G_{IC} increased by 57% and 106% respectively, with the integration of 2.5%wt. GNPs in the epoxy system [9]. Furthermore, Chandraserakan et al. presented that G_{IC} increased by 25% with the integration of 0.5%wt. GNPs in nano-composites [15]. Finally, Schulte et al. [16] studied the impact properties of CFRPs and GFRP reinforced with TRGOs. 19% and 55% increase was achieved in CFRPs and GFRPs respectively in compression after impact (CAI) property with the addition of 0.3%wt TRGO into the epoxy matrix.

The main aim of this article is to study the toughening effect of MWCNTs and GNPs in the CFRP laminates. For this reason two amounts of carbon nano-species (0.5 and 1%wt.) were dispersed in the epoxy resin using high shear mixing techniques. The produced nano-modified polymers were used as matrix material for the manufacturing of carbon fiber reinforced plastics. Mode I and mode II tests were performed and the fracture energy as a function of the nano-material content was evaluated. Finally, toughening mechanisms of carbon nano-fillers were presented by fracture surface observation composites with nano-reinforced matrix through scanning electron microscopy.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Materials

The matrix material, used in this study, was an epoxy prepreg system supplied by Huntsman Advanced materials, Switzerland. This system contains the low-viscosity epoxy resin Araldite LY1556, the hardener paste Aradur 1571, the accelerator paste 1573 and the polyamine hardener Aradur XB 3403.

The multi-wall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) produced by catalyzed chemical vapor deposition (CVD), were purchased from Arkema, France. MWCNTs were 98% pure with an average outer diameter of about 10-15nm, a length more than 500nm and a surface area of approximately 230m²/g. The graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) were 97% pure and obtained from Cheap Tube Inc., USA. GNPs consist of 20-25 graphene layers with an average thickness of 10-12nm and a typical diameter of 5 microns while their surface area was about 100m²/g.

Finally, a unidirectional carbon fabric, supplied by R&G, Germany, with an areal density of 140 g/m² was used as the main reinforcement of the composites.

2.2 Nano-reinforced matrix

The appropriate amounts of MWCNTs and GNPs were incorporated in the epoxy resin. The dispersion of nano-doped mixture took place in a dissolver device (Dispermat AE, VMA Getzmann GmbH). This technique leads to the introduction of high shear forces and vortex flow in the nano-enhanced mixture during stirring which are responsible for the reduction of the agglomeration between carbon particles. The mixing speed was maintained at 2500 rpm for 3.5h and the compounds were stirred in a vacuum container in order to eliminate the entrapped air during the mixing. Afterwards, the hardener was added to the prepared mixture and placed again in a vacuum chamber to eliminate air inclusion. Following the above process four different types of nano-reinforced matrices in contents of 0.5 and 1 % wt. were developed: MWCNT and GNP modified epoxy system.

2.3 Nano-reinforced CFRP laminates

The aforementioned prepared carbon nano-modified mixtures were used for the impregnation of unidirectional fabrics with a view to produce pre-impregnated fabrics according to the manual prepreg technique. Neat epoxy was also used as matrix in order to obtain the reference materials properties. The fabric impregnation was carried out at room temperature while the b staging was succeeded by keeping the prepreg for 48h at RT according to manufacturer instructions. Then, the b-stage prepregs were used for the production of unidirectional CFRP laminates. Each panel was composed of 14 unidirectional plies and a 13- μ m thick PTFE film was added in the middle plane of each panel to generate the starter crack which is required according to ASTM D5528 standard in order to perform the fracture tests. For the production of CFRPs a combination of compression molding method with vacuum bag technique was used in a curing and pressure profile according to manufacturer.

2.4 Experimental section

The resistance to interlaminar crack propagation of the produced composites was defined by performing two types of fracture toughness experiments on a hydraulic universal testing machine (Instron 8872). Five samples were tested for each type of material system and for each type of experiment. The opening Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{IC} , was determined by using the double cantilever beam (DCB) method and was carried out in accordance with ASTM Standard, D5528. The experiments were performed with a crosshead speed of 0.5mm/min. The load, P , and the corresponding displacement, δ , were recorded as a function of the crack length (a). Taking into consideration the rotation at the delamination front and that the DCB was not perfectly built-in, G_{IC} , was calculated according to the modified-beam theory as follows:

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{3P\delta}{2b(a+|\Delta|)}$$

Where b is the width of the specimen and Δ was determined experimentally by generating a least square fit on the cube root of compliance, $C^{1/3}$, against the crack length. The compliance, C , is the ratio of the displacement to the applied load δ/P , for a specific crack length.

The Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{IIc} , was measured by using the three-point end-notched flexure (3ENF) test at a loading rate of 1mm/min. G_{IIc} was calculated by using the elastic beam theory as follows:

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{9P^2Ca^2}{2B(2L^3 + 3a^3)}$$

where P is the applied load at the midspan, C is the compliance, a is the crack length, B is the specimens width, and L is the span length. The compliance calculated by using the following formula, based on the beam theory:

$$C = \frac{2L^3 + 3a^3}{8EBh^3}$$

where E the modulus in the fiber direction.

Finally, the fracture surfaces of the tested coupons were studied by using a LEO SUPRA 35VP Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following Figures present the calculated interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{IC} & G_{IIC} , obtained by implementing the aforementioned analysis. The resulting values G_{IC} & G_{IIC} are averaged and summarized in Figures 1 and 2 respectively for all samples. The error bars correspond to maximum and minimum values. As a general impression, the incorporation of carbon nano-fillers into the epoxy matrix proved beneficial for the improvement of fracture properties of the final composite. This is due to the extra energy required in the doped composites compared to the reference material for the evolution of the crack. The presence of nano-fillers into the matrix usually introduces additional toughening mechanisms in composites which are responsible for the higher energy observed in CFRPs with nano-reinforced matrix.

3.1 Mode I DCB tests

Figure 1: Interlaminar fracture energy in mode I CFRP composites

Mode I fracture energy for each prepared CFRP is depicted in **Figure 1**. It was observed that the incorporation of MWCNTs caused higher improvement in comparison with that of GNPs in this failure type. Furthermore, the increasing of filler content into the epoxy matrix did not cause any further enhancement in fracture toughness of the final composite. Significantly, it can be seen that the integration of 1%wt. MWCNTs achieved the highest increase (36%) in G_{IC} . Also, the addition of 0.5%wt. GNPs enhanced 27% the G_{IC} property while marginally higher enhancement (31%) achieved with the incorporation of MWCNTs into the matrix at the same content.

3.2 Mode II ENF tests

Figure 2: Interlaminar fracture energy in mode II for CFRP composites

The Mode II fracture toughness of the developed materials is presented in **Figure 2**. In this failure type, in contrast to Mode I results, the presence of GNPs exhibited the highest enhancement in interlaminar fracture toughness of final composites. Specifically, it can be seen in Figure 2 that the major enhancement (50%) in G_{IIc} achieved in the case of 0.5%wt. GNP composite. Also, it is worth mentioning that as in the case of Mode I tests, the increasing content of GNPs decreased the Mode II fracture toughness of composites. On the other hand, the introduction of highest content of MWCNTs into the matrix caused a further improvement in Mode II fracture toughness compared to composites doped with 0.5%wt. MWCNTs. Specifically, the addition of 1%wt. MWCNTs into the epoxy matrix achieved an increase of 35% while only 14% improvement succeeded with the incorporation of MWCNTs in content of 0.5%wt.

Both nano-species significantly increase the fracture toughness of CFRPs compared to the composite with unmodified epoxy resin matrix due to the additional toughening/energy dissipation mechanisms that introduce during the crack propagation. According to literature [1-5,17], in case of composites doped with CNTs, pull out of nanotubes, de-bonding and pinning of crack seems to contribute to the increase of their fracture energy. On the other hand, crack tip bifurcation upon its meeting with the nano-particles, separation between the graphitic layers and the shear failure of the matrix (due to the difference in height observed on fracture surfaces) are the extra failure mechanisms that have been observed in graphene-based composites [15].

It is obvious from **Figures 1 and 2** that MWCNTs are more promising fillers for the enhancement of Mode I fracture toughness while GNPs proved more appropriate toughening nano-inclusions in order to improve Mode II fracture toughness. This is probably due to the more efficient contribution of pull out mechanisms, offered from MWCNTs, in tensile loading type (Mode I) and to the more

effective activation of extra toughening mechanisms (bifurcation/separation of layers), introducing from GNPs, in shear loading type (Mode II). The aforementioned mechanisms are presented in detail in the fractographic analysis in the following section.

Finally, the degradation of fracture properties with the increasing content of GNPs can be attributed to a possible aggregation of particles due to the strong van der Waals forces that usually developed between carbon particles. GNPs seem to be more susceptible to this phenomenon than MWCNTs in the highest content of 1%wt. A possible explanation is that GNPs are bigger particles than MWCNTs. In particular, the diameter of GNPs is in micro-scale while the length of MWCNTs ranges in nano-scale.

3.3 Fractographic Analysis

Figure 3 presents the fracture surfaces of the baseline and nano- modified CFRPs after the fracture tests. The composite with neat epoxy (reference) appears a smooth fracture surface associated with the brittle behavior of epoxy matrix while the composites containing nano-modified matrix exhibit rougher matrix fracture surfaces against to that of the neat epoxy. This is due to the more macroscopically ductile failure of the nano-doped matrix in comparison with that of reference material.

Figure 3: SEM images of representative fracture surfaces of neat and nano-reinforced composites after fracture tests at different magnifications: a) neat, b) 0.5%wt. GNPs and c) 0.5%wt. MWCNTs

The following figures present the absorption mechanisms that were observed in fracture surfaces of doped composites.

Figure 4: SEM images of CNT failure mechanisms: pinning and pull out mechanisms at different magnifications

Figure 5: SEM images of GNP failure mechanisms at different magnifications: a) and b) bifurcation and pinning of crack tip; (c) and (d) pull out and separation between graphene layers

4 CONCLUSION

This study dealt with the use of MWCNTs and GNPs as nano-reinforcement for the epoxy matrix of CFRP laminates. Two different nano-filler contents (0.5 & 1% wt.) were used and compared to the reference material. The dispersion of nano-fillers into the epoxy matrix was carried out using dissolver technique while the development of nano-modified carbon fiber/epoxy laminates fabricated according to the manual prepreg technique in combination with compression molding procedure.

The results indicated the positive effect of these fillers on the fracture behavior of the final composites. In mode I loading the presence of 1%wt. MWCNTs in the epoxy led to a remarkable increase of fracture energy (36%) while the addition of 0.5%wt. GNPs caused the major enhancement of 50% in the case of Mode II experiments. This trend is closely connected to the additional toughening mechanisms, confirmed by SEM, which are introduced from the nano-fillers in the composite. In the case of tensile loading (Mode I), pinning and pull out mechanisms of CNTs constituted the key factor for the improvement of G_{IC} while the most effective activation of GNP extra absorption mechanisms (bifurcation/separation between layers) in shear loading (Mode II) determined the GNPs more promising nano-filler in comparison with the CNTs for the enhancement of G_{IIc} property.

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